

DEVELOPMENT OF CONSTRUCTION OF ENERGY EFFICIENT BUILDINGS

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Abstract: Ways and details of to improve energy efficitncy and rational use of buildings under construction as well as work carried out in this direction Uzbekistan and countries of the world are described

Keywords: Energy-efficient house, energy source, active house, building, thermal insulation, power consumption, power consumption, energy audit.

INTRODUCTION

One of the modern trends in housing construction is to carry out design and construction works taking into account the comfort, environmental and energy efficiency of the houses that are planned to be built.

As we know, the main sources of energy in the world are reserves (oil, gas and coal). According to experts' calculations, energy sources can last up to 100 years. In many developed countries, almost half of energy consumption is in housing. Therefore, one of the main ways to save resources is to improve the energy efficiency of buildings.

At the initial stage of the development of energy-efficient houses in Uzbekistan, there is a lack of incentive mechanisms and concepts of energy saving in construction, similar to the German standard passive houses (Passivhaus).

One of the main factors limiting the introduction of energy-saving technology is the fact that 1 m² of living space of an energy-efficient residential building is more than 812% more expensive than 1 m² of a conventional residential building. Therefore, many companies finance the construction of energy-wasting residential buildings and thereby ensure high profits.

A slightly different approach to energy conservation has developed in commercial real estate construction. Here, the client seeks to improve the thermal properties of the building and reduce utility costs. At the same time, the additional costs incurred to increase the energy efficiency of the building will be returned within 7-10 years. Therefore, energy-saving technologies are quite common in the construction of commercial real estate: banks, administrative buildings, office and commercial buildings.

The main principle of designing an energy-efficient house is the sustainable construction of the building and, therefore, through the use of alternative energy sources is able to maintain a comfortable internal temperature without using ventilation and heating systems.

The criteria for classifying such houses is energy consumption: if annual building heating costs are less than 90 kvh/m², the house is considered energy efficient; Less than 45 kWh/m² is less energy efficient; Less than 15 kWh / m² energy consumption is considered zero (nothing is spent on heating, but energy is required to prepare hot water).

The first experimental energy-efficient building appeared in Manchester (USA) in 1974 after the global energy crisis.

METHODS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This was an office building requested by the Office of General Services to test and identify the best energy saving technical solutions. The building's energy consumption has been reduced due to efficient use of solar radiation, double-layer closed structures and computer control of the building's engineering equipment. The implementation of this project laid the foundation for the construction of energy-efficient buildings around the world. Efforts to improve energy efficiency are being successfully implemented in Europe. According to various sources, from 2,000 to 10,000 such houses were built in Western European countries.

Targeted state programs have been developed in Denmark, Germany and Finland for such energy saving and construction of energy-efficient buildings.

10 kilometers outside Helsinki, the capital of Finland, is Vikki, a neighborhood of energy-efficient buildings (local population 5,500 and land area 1,132 hectares). It accounts for 50 percent of the neighborhood's solar energy use and hot water needs.

The total area of solar collectors is 1248 m². Energy-saving technology and alternative energy consumption can reduce energy consumption by 40% compared to conventional houses.

Denmark is currently the city of Egedal. In accordance with the state program, the construction of all energy-efficient residential buildings was carried out in South Stenlos. These local citizens are not limited to ecological and energy-saving buildings, but also provide ready-made houses equipped with all energy-saving innovations.

The following constructive and engineering planning solutions are used to minimize energy consumption.

From the point of view of planning, to reduce the area of the walls of 1-3-story houses and their facades (glazing) and thereby prevent heat loss.

At the same time, the main thing is to design a drum at the entrance and build the house facing south, because the main source of heat for heating the house is solar energy.

The houses are prevented from being shaded by other buildings and trees. The heat transfer resistance of the walls should not exceed 0.15 kW/m², for this, internal or double (internal and external) thermal insulation is used.

Today, in our Republic, the development of the way of living of the population in rural areas, the construction of houses on the basis of model projects is inextricably linked with the development of rural infrastructures and the establishment of infrastructure facilities. Many houses and apartments based on model projects in accordance with the "Program for the construction of affordable housing on updated model projects in rural areas in 2017-2021" approved by the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-2639 dated October 21, 2016 was built and a family in need of improvement of living conditions was

provided with housing. Also, in our country, today attention is paid to the issue of building energy-efficient, economical houses as one of the most important factors in the development of the construction industry, and in particular, the residential buildings and social sector buildings that are being built on the basis of model projects in rural and urban areas within the framework of state programs Enrichment with these features is defined as the main task.

Decree No. PF-5577 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, adopted on November 14, 2018, "On additional measures to improve state regulation of the construction industry", starting from January 1, 2020, housing construction It is strictly determined that facilities must be equipped with energy-efficient and energy-saving equipment at the stage of design-research and construction-assembly work. In this regard, our project "Supporting the development of energy-efficient rural housing construction in Uzbekistan", which has been implemented since 2017 in cooperation with the Global Ecology Fund and the Ministry of Construction of the Republic of Uzbekistan, deserves attention. As a result of the implementation of the project, it is expected that energy consumption and greenhouse gas emissions will decrease in households.

800 three-room energy-efficient houses with low carbon were built in Samarkand, Surkhandarya, Fergana, Khorezm and Bukhara regions within the framework of the project "Supporting the development of energy-efficient rural housing construction in Uzbekistan". Each of these houses has 300 Watt Photoelectric Plants (FES) installed and operating for lighting needs. Ten such houses are equipped with solar water heaters capable of heating 200 liters of water. However, such a level of energy consumption in the building remains for 3 to 5 years, and then begins to increase again. An energy audit is necessary to determine the reasons for this decrease in energy efficiency. Therefore, it is recommended to conduct an energy audit once every four years. It is worth mentioning that 800 energy-efficient houses built in 2019 within the framework of our project "Supporting the development of energy-efficient rural housing construction in Uzbekistan" in cooperation with the Ministry of Construction of the Republic of

Uzbekistan have installed 300-watt photoelectric power. stations (FES) are installed. An energy audit will be conducted in 60 houses selected from among these constructed buildings and ordinary model houses built in 2018 within the framework of the State program. This approach makes it possible to compare energy-efficient houses with ordinary houses and to analyze the effectiveness of using energy-efficient and low-carbon technologies in reducing heat and electricity consumption in rural houses.

CONCLUSION

The widespread introduction of energy audits, the use of renewable energy sources is one of the important and still not fully exploited reserves. It will help solve the problem of natural gas and oil shortages in the future and, according to experts, it can double the energy costs of consumers.

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